

LABOR MOBILIZATION IN TURKESTAN

Farkhod Ergashev

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8049474>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 12-June 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 15-June 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 17-June 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Turkestan, Tsarist Russia, labor, volost, village

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the causes and consequences of the 1916 national liberation movement against labor in Turkestan.

Uzbeks, Tajiks, Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, Karakalpaks and other peoples who fell under the yoke of colonialism and national oppression inflicted unprecedented oppression and suffering on their heads, and the national culture, values, traditions and national identity of these peoples were destroyed. 'ururur was trampled. This kind of oppression aroused deep hatred in the hearts of the people of Turkestan, and this hatred was passed from generation to generation. Therefore, the people of Turkestan revolted several times against the colonial policy of Tsarist Russia. In this regard, the uprisings against "labor" in 1892, 1898 and 1916 left an indelible mark on the pages of history. These insurgents were connected to each other on the basis of historical logic and marched under the banner of independence and freedom.

Their difference from each other was that the impact of the uprisings of 1892 and 1898 spread throughout the country, but they arose and intensified within a certain region. The uprising of 1916 was very extensive and violent, and its echo spread throughout Russia and shook it. The distinctive features of these uprisings are that there was not a single city or village that did not participate in them or did not express sympathy, and peasants, artisans, workers and other categories of the population came to the field of struggle as a guiding force. Also, advanced representatives of the local upper classes took part in the uprisings. In the course of this struggle, the unity, cooperation and friendship of Uzbeks, Tajiks, Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Turkmen and Karakalpaks emerged and grew stronger. They sacrificed their lives for independence and freedom, considering the vast land of Turkestan as a "common home".

It is worth noting that women also actively participated in the uprisings that broke out in cities and villages. In some places, women were the first to start the uprising. This situation testifies to the fact that national tyranny has aroused deep-rooted resentment and hatred of women.

Except for the Russians, almost all the settled and nomadic population of the region were affected by the 1916 uprising. The rebels included artisans, peasants, laborers, and other

poor people. Therefore, it is appropriate to clarify the situation of those professions. In particular, crafts were widespread in cities and large villages. Historically formed dyeing, tailoring, pottery, coppersmithing, carpentry, shoemaking, carpentry, patchwork, tanning, hat making, blacksmithing, and dozens of other various crafts have taken an important place in everyday life. Even handicraft products were taken to foreign countries. Although handicrafts did not lose their importance even after the establishment of the rule of Tsarist Russia, some of their types increasingly sank into the quagmire of the crisis. "The country's isolation from the outside world for many centuries, the absence of factories and factories, all the needs of the households of local residents have been met at the expense of various products obtained from the processing and preparation of raw materials," says a Russian source. Therefore, handicraft production in the region, including in Tashkent, has been greatly improved and developed not only from a practical, but also from an artistic point of view. Chests, saddles, clothes, leather, shoes, pottery, carpets, yarn, woolen and silk fabrics, and various other things all come from the hands of artisans¹.

In fact, products made by artisans in regions and cities, especially in Tashkent, are famous for their elegance and beauty. However, the large amount of factory and factory goods brought to the country caused great damage to handicrafts. In this regard, the same Russian source has the following information: "Recently, in some branches of handicrafts, there is a crisis and a retreat behind the introduction of goods from Russian factories and the recruitment of workers to enterprises that produce agricultural products needed for the Russian market. For example, the craft of tailoring, unable to withstand the competition of factory goods, declined greatly. However, local fabrics are much better in terms of weaving, quality and cost, and are in demand in the European market to a certain extent.

Although it is true that people are attracted to cotton ginning factories here, unemployed weavers and other craftsmen were forced to work in them. According to the same source, artisans did not have the opportunity to compete with factory goods due to poverty. "In general, the sources write that local craftsmen are considered to be very experienced people and have proven themselves to be skilled craftsmen in many manufactured items. But in order to make them able to produce goods that can meet today's demands and withstand factory products, it is necessary to introduce innovations in their work, provide material and cultural support. The first task is to provide basic support to the artisans by giving loans in time to buy necessary things and expand production. The second important factor is that it is necessary to unite the same artisans in one cooperative (company) to purchase products at the right price without intermediaries. It was impossible to implement such correct opinions in the colonial political framework. Because the Russian government and capitalists. it was said that he could not give up earning a profit by purchasing industrial goods. There are even reports that they implemented a policy of displacing Uzbek goods in places inhabited by nomadic peoples².

In general, handicrafts continued their activities despite being in extremely difficult conditions. According to some estimates, 20,000-25,000 people were engaged in handicrafts, and the produced product amounted to 10-12 million soums. A craftsman lived in a difficult situation because his annual income was around 400-500 soums. Thus, artisans could not

¹ Обзор Сыр-Дариньской области за 1913 г. Т. 1916.- С. 93.

² Хайдаров Х. Jizzax tarixidan lavhalar. Т. 1992. 26-bet

cope with the competition and were forced to become unemployed or work in temporary factories. The increasing importation of Russian goods and the generally harsh conditions and colonial policies all together led to the growing desire for freedom among the artisans. The living conditions of the farmers in the Syrdarya region were also very deplorable. As in other parts of the country, the Syrdarya region also started acclimatization of American cotton and achieved good results. On the surface, the development of cotton cultivation was considered an important event, but in practice it was a disaster for the farmers. Because mainly the Russian Empire and the local trade industry saw its benefits and "wept monkeys" over the plight of the local population. This situation worsened with the development of cotton farming. Therefore, it will be useful to know the growth process of cotton growing in the region.

The development of cotton cultivation in the country, including the Syrdarya region, began in the 1980s. If the area planted with cotton in this region was 23,541, 39,165 in 1907, 64,450,000 desyatinas in 1912, in 1915 it reached 74,050,000 desyatinas. However, although the cotton area increased and decreased depending on the weather and other conditions, there was no sharp decrease.

In 1897, 1,283,000 pounds of cotton were grown in Syrdarya region, and in 1913, its volume reached 3,9722 pounds. So, over the course of 15 years, it almost tripled, but almost all of the cotton was sent to Russia. The profits of cotton fell into the pockets of the tsarist government and capitalists. The hard work and suffering of growing it was a burden for the farmers. The plight of cotton farmers attracted the attention of some authors of that time. In one such book, "the farmer, who was in the vortex of debt and injustice, was always ready to give up cotton farming due to the destruction of his home. Even in it, the farmer is described as an "unfortunate grower". In fact, the lifestyle of growers is very difficult, and no effort has been made to satisfy their needs and demands. "The negative aspects of the measures aimed at the development of cotton production were that, writes V. I. Yuferov, - circles protecting the interests of the people were not involved in their preparation and implementation. All administrative measures were issued by the government, and the chamber of commerce and industry implemented its demands through the cotton committee under the Kokan stock exchange committee and the Moscow stock exchange committee.

When it comes to the farmers in the cotton growing regions, it must be said that they cannot be said to be an unorganized mass, to speak their needs and protect their interests. The societies established in the provincial cities united much larger landowners and were far from the mass of peasants. Therefore, agricultural societies could not sufficiently reflect the interests of the masses of peasants."

So, the farmer's life was very bad and he owed money to companies, local usurers and banks. As a result of their inability to repay debts on time, they increased more and more. Because the loan amount is much higher than the price of cotton, it was considered a burden on the farmer. In many cases, the loan money was distributed through the mediation of the representatives of the local ethnic groups.

References:

1. NAUz, fund 1, list 25, case 24. Sheet 109.
2. Xaydarov X. Jizzax tarixidan lavhalar. T. 1992. 19-bet.
3. O'zbekiston tarixi. 1 jild, ikkinchi kitob, T.: 2011.-B. 110.